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Inflationary Universe

Misael Arnaldo Espinal Valladares¹

¹ *Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation
Honduran Institute of Science, Technology and Innovation
SENACIT/IHCIETI*

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Abstract: Studying the universe, understanding its origin and evolution has always been of great interest to humanity. In this context, cosmology proposes it, seeking to answer questions related to its structure, composition, and dynamics. Initially, there were various proposed models, but the one that has achieved considerable success when compared with different cosmological observations was the Hot Big Bang model. This implies a universe in expansion, homogeneous and isotropic on a large scale, that is, there are no preferred points or directions in the universe (WEINBERG, 2008). However, despite its great success, it has some problems, among them the horizon and flatness problems can be highlighted. A widely accepted proposal to solve them is that the universe, at its initial moment, underwent a phase of exponential growth. Such a proposal constitutes what is known as inflationary models, which, in addition to solving the problems present in the Hot Big Bang model, provides a good explanation for the formation of the anisotropies of the universe as a result of the expansion of quantum fluctuations in the scalar field generating the inflationary period called inflaton.

Keywords: Cosmology, Hot Big Bang, Inflation, Inflaton, Scalar Field.

1 Introduction

Based on cosmological observations, there were several models proposed to explain the workings of the universe. Among these, one stood out and earned recognition from the scientific community, the Hot Big Bang model. This model is based on several important theoretical pillars, including the cosmological principle, which states that when observed on a large scale, the universe is homogeneous and isotropic, meaning there are no preferred points or directions in the universe.

It also hypothesizes that the dynamics of the universe at all scales can be described by Einstein's general theory of relativity and assumes that the content of the universe can be described as a perfect fluid. (VAZQUEZ; PADILLA; MATOS, 2020).

This model has yielded very satisfactory results compared to observations. Among its successes, one can cite the correct prediction of the temperature of the cosmic microwave background radiation, the abundance of elements, and perhaps its most famous consequence, the evidence of

an accelerating universe expansion. It is important to note that astronomical data indicates that galaxies are receding at a speed proportional to their distance, this does not mean that the Milky Way is the center of the universe, as the cosmological principle ensures there can be no privileged point in space (a common analogy to exemplify the expansion of the universe).

Despite these and several other successes of the Hot Big Bang model, there are still observed phenomena that cannot be explained by this model. It is with this motivation that to remedy these found problems, inflationary cosmological models emerge (GUTH, 1981). With an interesting proposal that the universe, at its initial moment, underwent a phase of exponential growth, inflationary models suggest complementing the Hot Big Bang, solving its problems, and still providing a good explanation for the formation of the universe's anisotropies through the expansion of quantum fluctuations in the inflation-generating field (inflaton).

2 Inflationary Theory

Initially, the universe was hot and dense, filled with interacting particles. It has been conjectured that prior to this phase, the universe underwent a brief period of accelerated expansion known as inflation when quantum fluctuations, stretched to cosmologically large scales, became the seeds for the universe's stars and galaxies. According to inflation theory, as the universe expands exponentially fast, its geometry becomes flat; this geometry was experimentally confirmed around the year

2000. Subsequently, theorists had to use the laws of physics to solve the problem of how to stop inflation so that the universe could cool and structure begin to form (THOMAS, 2014).

“The standard model of Hot Big Bang cosmology requires initial conditions that are problematic in two ways: (1) the early universe is assumed to be highly homogeneous, despite the fact that separated regions were causally disconnected (the horizon problem); and (2) the initial value of the Hubble constant must be set with extraordinary precision to produce a universe as flat (i.e., close to the critical mass density) as we see today (the flatness problem). These problems would disappear if, in its early history, the universe supercooled to temperatures 28 or more orders of magnitude below the critical temperature for some phase transition. A huge expansion factor would then result from a period of exponential growth, and the entropy of the universe would be multiplied by a huge factor when latent heat was released. Such a scenario is completely natural in the context of grand unified models of elementary particle interactions. In such models, supercooling is also relevant to the problem of monopole annihilation. Unfortunately, the scenario seems to lead to some unacceptable consequences, so modifications must be sought (GUTH, 1981).”

3 The Hot Big Bang

The Hot Big Bang model describes a universe that obeys the cosmological principle, and its evolution is determined by the Friedmann equations derived from Ein-

stein's field equations (COLES, 2002).

3.1 Homogeneity and Isotropy

The cosmological principle states that the Universe, on cosmological scales, is homogeneous and isotropic (FIXSEN, 2009). Homogeneity means that any point in the Universe looks the same and has the same properties as any other given point. Isotropy means that no matter in which direction one is looking, the same properties will be observed in the Universe (this applies to large scales), on small scales the universe is neither homogeneous nor isotropic.

3.2 The FLRW Metric

$$ds^2 = \left[dr^2(1 - kr^2)^{-1} + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \right] [-a^2(t)] + dt^2 \quad (1)$$

The expression above is the Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker metric, which brings together the characteristics of geometric theory that describes the universe.

3.2.1 Friedmann Equations

The Friedmann equations are a set of equations that govern the metric expansion of space in models that comply with the cosmological principle as established in the General Theory of Relativity.

To describe the general properties of the Universe, it is assumed that its dynamics are described as a perfect fluid with pressure $p(t)$ and energy density $\rho(t)$. Both quantities are often related through an equation of state in the form of $p = p(\rho)$.

component	$\rho(a)$	$a(t)$	$H(t)$
radiation	$\propto a^{-4}$	$\propto t^{1/2}$	$1/(2t)$
matter	$\propto a^{-3}$	$\propto t^{2/3}$	$2/(3t)$
cosmological constant	$\propto a^0$	$\propto \exp(\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}}t)$	const

Figure 1: Evolution of $\rho(a)$, $a(t)$, and $H(t)$ when the universe is dominated by radiation, matter, or a cosmological constant (VAZQUEZ; PADILLA; MATOS, 2020).

The most studied cases are the following three:

1. Radiation:

$$p = \frac{\rho}{3} \quad (2)$$

2. Matter (dust):

$$p = 0 \quad (3)$$

3. Cosmological constant:

$$p = -\rho \quad (4)$$

The Einstein equations for these types of constituents, with the FLRW metric, are given by the Friedmann equation:

$$H^2 \equiv \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^2 = \frac{8\pi}{3m_{Pl}^2} \rho - \frac{k}{a^2} \quad (5)$$

The acceleration equation is:

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi}{3m_{Pl}^2} (\rho + 3p) \quad (6)$$

The continuity equation is:

$$\dot{\rho} + 3H(\rho + p) = 0 \quad (7)$$

Another form to express the Friedmann equations (commonly known as the first and second Friedmann equation) is:

First Friedmann equation:

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8}{3}\pi G\rho - c^2 k a^{-2} \quad (8)$$

Second Friedmann equation:

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4}{3}\pi G\left(\rho + 3\frac{P}{c^2}\right) \quad (9)$$

3.3 Problems of the Hot Big Bang

The inflationary theory solves two problems of the Hot Big Bang model, these are: the Flatness and Horizon problems (NASTASE; SKENDERIS, 2020).

3.3.1 Flatness Problem

From the first Friedmann equation, the term $\frac{3H^2}{8\pi G}$ is a critical density for a flat universe, so $|1 - \Omega| \approx 0$.

$$1 - \Omega = -R_H^2 k^2 \quad (10)$$

It is remarkable that from its origin to our time $\Omega \approx 1$. Our Universe in the past had to be flatter; the one we know in the present is approximately flat (PLANCK COLLABORATION, 2020).

3.3.2 Horizon Problem

The particle horizon increases with a and t , it was smaller in the past. Particles entering the horizon in the present were very far away in the past, this is if $\omega = \frac{1}{3}$ and $\omega = 0$ (MARTÍNEZ, 2016).

The CMB shows (based on the Hot Big Bang model) 1,000,000 causally disconnected regions, these should have been causally connected because at a $T = 2.725$ K the CMB is isotropic.

$$2(1 + 3\omega)^{-1} H_0^{-1} a^{\left(\frac{1+3\omega}{2}\right)} \quad (11)$$

4 Inflationary Model

The flatness and horizon problems are solved by the Inflationary Model, which consists of the accelerated expansion our universe experienced at an early time.

4.1 Amount of Inflation (Number of e-folds)

The size of the expansion during the inflationary period is very large, the amount of inflation from a period of t to t_f in terms of the number of e-folds (N) (LYTH; RIOTTO, 1999) is governed by the following expression:

$$N = \ln \frac{a(t_f)}{a(t)} = \int_t^{t_f} H dt = \int_\phi^{\phi_f} H(\dot{\phi})^{-1} d\phi \quad (12)$$

For the slow-roll approximation it takes the following form:

$$N = 8\pi G \int_{\phi_f}^{\phi} V(V')^{-1} d\phi \quad (13)$$

4.2 Solution to the Flatness Problem

It is solved by inflation, a decreasing comoving Hubble radius would cause Ω to approach 1, during the inflationary period the universe would tend towards flatness instead of moving away from it.

From the equation of the flatness problem, $|1 - \Omega| \approx 0$, $R_H^2 \approx e^{-2N}$ where $N = 60$.

4.3 Solution to the Horizon Problem

For the horizon problem, it is important to clearly understand the distinction between the concepts of Particle Horizon χ_p

and Hubble Horizon $(aH)^{-1}$. If events are separated by a distance greater than χ_p they could never have been in contact, since the distance separating them is greater than $(aH)^{-1}$. Now they cannot be in contact, that is, it's possible that the particle horizon is much larger than the Hubble horizon, so particles cannot communicate in the current universe, but were in causal contact in the primordial universe.

Inflation solves this problem considering that the expanding universe behaves exponentially given by $a = a_i e^N$, $R_H(t_0) < R_H(t_i)$ where it would be necessary that $57 < N$ (CLESSE, 2015).

4.4 Conditions for Inflation

The conditions for the universe's decreasing Hubble radius and the models with this type of constraint are called inflationary models, and it is intended that:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(aH)^{-1} < 0 \quad (14)$$

The above condition can be rewritten as:

$$-\ddot{a}(aH)^{-2} < 0 \quad (15)$$

$$\ddot{a} > 0 \quad (16)$$

Where H is the Hubble constant and a the scale factor of the universe.

Cosmological inflation is defined as the period of accelerated expansion, so the equation can be expressed as:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(aH)^{-1} = -a^{-1}(1 - \epsilon) \quad (17)$$

and therefore, there is a condition of decreasing Hubble, resulting in:

$$\epsilon = -\dot{H}H^{-2} < 1 \quad (18)$$

In Einstein's field equation in natural units it is evident that being $\ddot{a} > 0$, then:

$$p < -\frac{1}{3}\rho \quad (19)$$

It is important to mention that matter and radiation do not satisfy the above condition. The cosmological constant is considered ideal to generate these solutions because a Λ -dominated universe can be $p = -\rho$ (a perfect fluid). Substituting this condition into the Friedmann equation would result in an exponentially expanding universe (VAZQUEZ; PADILLA; MATOS, 2020):

$$a(t) \propto \exp(\Lambda/3)^{\frac{1}{2}}t \quad (20)$$

Thus, the equation is satisfied.

In summary, inflation occurs when $\epsilon < 1$. To solve the horizon problem, it must have a duration of $N \approx 60$ e-folds, ϵ must remain at a small value for sufficient time, so the constraint that ensures this happens is given by:

$$\eta = \frac{d}{dN}(\ln \epsilon) = \dot{\epsilon}(H\epsilon)^{-1} \quad (21)$$

Therefore, for an accelerated expansion, $\epsilon \ll 1$ and $\eta \ll 1$ must hold, these are called slow-roll parameters.

4.5 Scalar Field Dynamics

A unique scalar field that generates accelerated expansion is called the inflaton. Initially considering that it can depend on

time as well as spatial position (CARROLL, 2019). Associated with each value of the field ϕ , there is a potential energy density $V(\phi)$. Therefore, the conditions under which this scalar field generates the inflationary period are sought. It will be used as a parameter to measure the evolution of inflation.

To study this dynamic, it can be described by a scalar field action term added to the Einstein-Hilbert action (UNANUÉ, 2011), as shown by the following expression:

$$S = \int d^4x (\mathcal{L}_\phi + \mathcal{L}_{E-H}) \quad (22)$$

From the Euler-Lagrange equations, the equations of motion can be obtained (CHENG, 2005):

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_\phi}{\partial \phi} - \partial_\mu \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial^\mu \phi)} = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - V(\phi) \quad (24)$$

In this case, performing it for the inflaton lagrangian obtains the motion equation or better known as the Klein-Gordon equation for the inflaton:

$$\ddot{\phi} + 3H\dot{\phi} + \frac{\partial V(\phi)}{\partial \phi} = 0 \quad (25)$$

The form for the energy-momentum tensor of the inflaton will be:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - g_{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - V(\phi) \right) \quad (26)$$

$$T_i^j = -p_\phi \delta_i^j \quad (27)$$

$$T_0^0 = \rho_\phi \quad (28)$$

Where T_i^j is the spatial component and T_0^0 the temporal component (MELIA, 2015).

The energy density is calculated with the energy-momentum tensor and has the following form:

$$\rho_\phi = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi) \quad (29)$$

and similarly the pressure, expressed as:

$$p_\phi = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\phi}^2 - V(\phi) \quad (30)$$

Substituting into the equation of state $p = \omega \rho$ and solving for ω :

$$\omega = \frac{p_\phi}{\rho_\phi} \quad (31)$$

$$\omega = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \dot{\phi}^2 - V(\phi)}{\frac{1}{2} \dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi)} \quad (32)$$

4.6 Slow-Roll Approximation

For inflation to persist long enough and resolve the horizon and flatness problems, certain conditions must be met. For the scalar field ϕ , some approximations can be taken that guarantee this property. The first is that the model starts from an almost flat potential, meaning $\dot{\phi}^2 \ll V(\phi)$; however, to ensure that this condition lasts long enough, a second approximation can be made where $|\ddot{\phi}| \ll V'(\phi)$.

First slow-roll condition:

$$\epsilon_V(\phi) = \frac{1}{16\pi G} \left(\frac{V'}{V} \right)^2 \quad (33)$$

$$|\epsilon_V(\phi)| \ll 1 \quad (34)$$

Second slow-roll condition:

$$\eta_V(\phi) = \frac{1}{8\pi G} \left(\frac{V''}{V} \right) \quad (35)$$

$$|\eta_V(\phi)| \ll 1 \quad (36)$$

4.7 End of Inflation

As the field ϕ rolls towards the potential minimum $V(\phi)$, the slow-roll conditions begin to lose their validity, and inflation ends. Therefore, it is natural to assume the end of inflation when $\epsilon_V = 1$ (LIDDLE; LYTH, 2000).

5 Conclusion

The importance of studying the inflationary universe is because it solves several of the problems present in the Hot Big Bang and, with the advancement of observational instruments, it is increasingly becoming a solid theory. From a brief review of Tensor Calculus and the Theory of General Relativity, the foundations of the Hot Big Bang model were formulated, highlighting its successes, its dynamics, in which the universe requires the assumption of initial conditions that are very implausible for two reasons: (i) The horizon problem. It is assumed that causally disconnected regions are almost identical; in particular, they are simultaneously at the same temperature. (ii) The flatness problem. For a fixed initial temperature, the initial value of the Hubble constant must be adjusted with extraordinary precision to produce a universe as flat as the one we observe. Both problems would disappear if the universe supercooled 28 or more orders of magnitude below the critical temperature for some phase transition. Under

such circumstances, the universe would be growing exponentially over time (GUTH, 1981), the main motivation for the development of inflationary models, where in this case with the unique scalar field, the equations of motion can be simplified due to the assumption that the scalar field is the only matter field present in the early Universe and thus, scalar fields are used in Cosmology to provide models for the unanswered enigmas of the universe (LÓPEZ, 2016).

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